

**ANALYSIS OF THE CREDIT PRACTICE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN)**

Eshonov Muhammadayub Xoshimjon o‘g‘li

Associate Professor, PhD, Andijan Institute of Economics and Construction

Nematullayev Hamidullo Azizillo o‘g‘li

Student of Andijan Institute of Economics and Construction

Abstract

This article describes the importance and necessity of loans allocated by commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the development of the economy. The dynamics of loans allocated for 2019-2023 and their changes are analyzed. Scientific proposals are formulated for the further development of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: commercial banks, loans, portfolio, corporate governance, financial asset, interest rate, online banking, currency, investment.

Introduction

The role of commercial banks in financing the activities of joint-stock companies is of great importance. Commercial banks, in addition to being an important source of financing the activities of joint-stock companies, also play a special role in developing their participation in the capital market. In recent years, several reforms have been implemented in our country to develop the capital market. This includes specific areas for improving financial relations between corporate structures and commercial banks. In addition, these include further improving the activities of commercial banks, in particular, diversifying banking services, increasing the level of bank capitalization, digitizing services provided by banks, and establishing an online banking system. Of course, as a result, the role of commercial banks in developing the capital market is increasing.

Based on the regions' economic and social potential and the population's needs, commercial banks are actively participating in socially significant projects and developing services. These include healthcare, trade and consumer services, tourism and hotel services, education, transport, construction and reconstruction of various facilities, IT-communications, and catering. In addition, in recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out from a legislative point of view to develop further cooperation in financing and comprehensive support for the activities of large industrial enterprises by commercial banks. The new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets out as one of its priority tasks “to complete the transformation processes in state-owned commercial banks and increase the share of the private sector in bank assets to 60 percent by the end of 2026”[1].

To ensure the effective implementation of these tasks, it is important to further accelerate the privatization of large joint-stock commercial banks, expand transformation processes, organize public placement of shares on local and foreign stock markets, and develop relations between commercial banks and international financial institutions.

Literature review

Domestic and foreign economists have studied the role of commercial banks in developing the national economy, their lending practices, participation in the securities market, and the improvement of banking activities.

In today's globalized and rapidly developing IT landscape, digital finance is developing as a key segment of the financial sector. The results of the study show that the development of digital finance increases the profitability of commercial banks, while strengthening their risk-taking ability and overall stability. It is worth noting that operational efficiency plays an important role in this process. Of course, the development of digital finance-banks in recent years has raised concerns about

job losses, but in the long term it can also serve as a basis for creating additional jobs in online banking services [2]. Commercial banks are considered one of the most important financial institutions in reducing the shadow economy along with developing the national economy. Of course, when analyzing the activities of commercial banks in the recent past, there are cases where the limitation of interference in their activities by the state and relevant regulatory authorities has also led to an increase in offshore or clandestine banking services by banks. It is precisely the determination of the optimal “point” for the development of financial supervision and banking activities that plays an important role in increasing the well-being of the national economy and the population [3]. Commercial banks play an important role in the allocation of capital by providing loans and credits to various sectors and areas of the economy. Through lending practices, banks serve the expansion of entrepreneurship, innovation and business, thereby stimulating economic activity and job creation. By assessing creditworthiness and managing risks, banks contribute to sustainable economic growth and ensure the flow of capital to promising projects and enterprises [4].

Rational management of the resources formed in banks and the structure of their sources allows to optimally satisfy the wide demand for credit in the economy, and on the other hand, it also increases the efficiency of using these resources in commercial banks [5]. Today, improving the interest rate policy of commercial banks is one of the necessary conditions for ensuring their financial stability and increasing the level of use of banking services by customers. In particular, failure to achieve the normative levels of net interest spread and net interest margin indicators in banks does not allow to ensure their financial stability [6]. The initial results of the reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to improve the banking system in recent years indicate that there are certain gaps between the formation of the fundamentals of banking activities and the measures being implemented. This situation primarily concerns strategic development programs

and directions that determine the state of the banking system in the near and long term [7]. Since loans occupy a relatively high share in the total assets of commercial banks, improving loan portfolio management is an important factor in ensuring the liquidity and financial stability of the bank. In turn, the main attention in managing the loan portfolio of commercial banks is paid to ensuring the stability of loan profitability and preventing an increase in the level of loan portfolio risks [8]. Based on the above-mentioned opinions of scientists, it can be said that in recent years, a new “vector” of the development of the banking system in our country has been formed and is being improved by international standards. In addition, commercial banks play an important role in the allocation and redistribution of financial resources in the capital market and are the main investors in the development of the securities market.

Analysis and results

In the context of the further improvement of the business environment in our country and the limited availability of alternative financing sources, the demand for bank loans to finance private sector investment projects remains high.

Figure 1. Growth in the balance of loans allocated to sectors of the economy (in %)¹

As of January 1, 2024, an increase in the volume of loans allocated was observed in all sectors of the economy, with the balance of loan investments in the industrial sector (a rise of 10.7 percent) amounting to 140.2 trillion soums, in agriculture (12.3 percent) to 47.3 trillion soums, in transport and communications (15.7 percent) to 34.3 trillion soums, in trade and catering (12.5 percent) to 32.5 trillion soums, and in construction (18 percent) to 12.3 trillion soums (Figure 1). In particular, in 2023, a total of 251.4 trillion soums, or about 24 percent more credit funds, were allocated to finance the economy, compared to 2022, and the total balance of credit investments reached about 497 trillion soums. The growing share of loans to the population in the structure of allocated loans is explained, in turn, by

¹ <https://cbu.uz/upload/medialibrary/c2e/jcu9sa4tbwawr6xfqqnyn4ivpbc7s2l1/Yillik-hisobot-2024.pdf>

the growth in the volume of loans to the population in the areas of microloans, mortgage loans and car loans due to the simplification of loan allocation processes and the expansion of the possibilities of remote banking services. The rapid growth of private investment is also of great importance in supporting economic development. In particular, in 2023, the volume of investments absorbed from all sources of financing in the economy increased by 22.1 percent in real terms compared to 2022, reaching 352.1 trillion soums. reached soums. At the same time, decentralized investments increased by 26.2% compared to 2022 and amounted to 307.3 trillion soums, while centralized investments decreased by 0.7% and amounted to 44.8 trillion soums.

In order to meet the economy's demand for credit and provide financial support to business entities, banks allocated 251 trillion soums in loans in 2023, or 24% more than in 2022. At the same time, 60% of these loans fell on loans to business entities and 40% on loans to the population. In particular, it was noted that the share of loans allocated by private banks in total loans allocated in 2023 will increase from 31% to 43%, and their share in loans allocated to corporate clients will increase from 25% to 34% (Figure 2).

**Figure 2. Dynamics of loans and loan portfolio allocated in 2019-2023
(trln.sum)²**

Also, in 2023, the share of the balance of credit investments in the national currency increased by 2 percentage points compared to 2022 and amounted to 55 percent, while the share of loans in foreign currency decreased by 2 percentage points and amounted to 45 percent of the total loan portfolio. The decrease in the share of the balance of loans in foreign currency in the loan portfolio is explained by the increase in the cost of resources attracted from abroad, the increase in the level of repayment of loans in foreign currency (from 69 percent in 2022 to 89 percent), and the increasing skills (experience) of business entities in hedging against currency exchange rate risks.

The balance of allocated loans by economic sectors increased by 10.7% to 140.2 trillion soums in the industrial sector, by 12.3% to 47.3 trillion soums in agriculture, by 15.7% to 34.3 trillion soums in transport and communications, by 12.5% to 32.5 trillion soums in trade and catering, and by 18% to 12.3 trillion soums

² <https://cbu.uz/oz/publications/annual-report/> - ma'lumotlari asosida muallif tomonidan tayyorlandi

in construction. The improvement of corporate governance of commercial banks, the entry of digital foreign banks into the country's banking market, and the increase in the scale of remote customer service are creating the basis for an increase in lending volumes to the economy based on market principles.

In particular, during 2023, the balance of preferential loans¹³ increased by 5% (6 trillion soums), reaching 145 trillion soums at the end of the year, but their share in the total allocated loans decreased from 36% at the beginning of last year to 31% at the beginning of this year. In 2023, special attention is paid to creating conditions for meeting the economy's growing demand for loans and attracting long-term domestic financing sources to the banking system against the backdrop of increasing resource prices and increased competition in the external resource market for its attraction. In particular, in 2023, the total liabilities of banks reached 555 trillion soums, and this indicator increased by 16% or 78 trillion soums compared to 2022. 48% of the growth in liabilities was formed by attracted credit funds, 32% by deposits, 7% by local interbank loans and deposits, 4% by subordinated loans and 9% by other liabilities.

In 2022, the total assets of commercial banks increased by 25%, reaching 557 trillion soums as of January 1, 2023, with loan deposits accounting for 70% of assets. Banks allocated 203 trillion soums in 2022 for the purpose of financial support of the population and business entities, or 22% more loans than in 2021, and the total balance of bank loans exceeded 390 trillion soums. Of these loans, 68 percent (138 trillion soums) were directed to corporate clients and 32 percent (65 trillion soums) to the population, while the high level of return on previously allocated loans to bank turnover (67 percent) remained, serving as the main source of financing the economy. Continuing our analysis based on the data in Figure 2, in 2021, banks will allocate 166.7 trillion soums to meet the economy's demand for credit and provide financial support to businesses. In the amount of soums or 28 percent more loans were directed than the target indicator for lending (130 trillion

soums), 76 percent of these loans (126 trillion soums) were allocated to corporate clients and 24 percent (41 trillion soums) to the population. In turn, as a result of the use of modern approaches such as “Pre-collection” (0), “Soft-collection” (1-30), “Hardcollection” (30+), “Legal-collection” (90+) in banks to increase the efficiency of loan collection in the event of default and return financial resources to bank circulation, the loan recovery rate increased from 59 percent to 71 percent in 2021, and the growth rate of loan deposits was formed within the framework of nominal GDP growth rates (18 percent).

Conclusions and recommendations

Although global inflation slowed in 2024, the implementation of programs aimed at preventing imbalances in the economy, in the context of the continued high cost of resources in the international financial market, required the state to continue providing financial support to the economy. In order to reduce the inflationary pressures of pro-cyclical fiscal policy, fiscal and monetary policies were coordinated through a relatively tight monetary policy.

The results of the analysis of the banking sector show that the banking sector in Uzbekistan is developing dynamically, and the presence of problem loans and external risks is one of the main factors affecting financial stability. Over the past reporting years, to prevent the negative impact of problem loans on the financial stability of the banking system and reduce their weight, bank loan portfolios have been regularly analyzed by banks, regions, and segments. Specific measures are being developed to eliminate the identified shortcomings and problems.

The need to improve liquidity positions and financial stability is the basis for ensuring the confidence of customers and investors. It should be noted that the Center for Economic Research and Reforms updated the "Banking Activity Index" for the third quarter of 2024, covering 31 commercial banks in our country, taking into account the fact that banks consist of 17 large and 14 small banks by volume

of activity. The index is based on 27 coefficients, which allows for systematic analysis and comparison with average indicators for the republic and is calculated in accordance with the requirements of the Basel Committee. This rating is an important tool for assessing the stability of the banking sector of Uzbekistan and serves to further develop the country's financial system.

According to the results of the analysis, in the third quarter of 2024, the banking sector of Uzbekistan demonstrates significant stability and growth among large and small banks. In the overall ratings, large financial institutions maintain their strong positions, which, in turn, plays an important role in adapting to external changes and developing the competitive environment in the market. The improvement in the financial performance of individual banks indicates positive trends in financial attractiveness and liquidity. Active investment and financial development are observed in the segment of small banks. At the same time, the need for constant monitoring and adjustment of management strategies remains relevant, which will allow all market participants to strengthen their positions and increase overall financial stability.

Despite the increase in foreign currency assets and the positive trend in global gold prices, the decline in the net international investment position was mainly due to the attraction of external debt and foreign investments by the state, banks, and other private sector enterprises.

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